

1 Scenario 1 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S1 rule1"
trigger
  always
condition
  front_vehicle_closer_than(10)
then
  follow_dist(10)
  yield_dist(15)
  overtake_dist(20)
  dynamic_obstacle_stop_dist(10)
  dynamic_obstacle_decrease_ratio(1)
end

rule "S1 rule2"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(red)
  traffic_light_distance_leq(10)
then
  trsffic_light_stop_dist(5)
end
```

2 Scenario 2 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S9 rule1"
trigger always condition front_static_obstacle_closer_than(6.5)
then
  static_obstacle_decrease_ratio(0.8)
  stop
end

rule "S9 rule2"
trigger always condition front_vehicle_speed_smaller_than(3.6)
then
  obstacle_dec(True)
  dynamic_obstacle_decrease_ratio(0.6)
end

rule "S9 rule3"
trigger always condition stop_sign_closer_than(6.5)
then
  stop_sign_check(True)
  stop_sign_stop_dist(6.5)
  stop_sign_wait_time(8)
  stop_sign_crawl_time(10)
end
```

3 Scenario 3 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S2 rule1"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(yellow)
  traffic_light_distance_leq(5)
then
  stop
end

rule "S2 rule2"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(yellow)
  traffic_light_distance_leq(50)
then
  max_plan_speed(21)
  cruise_speed(21)
end

rule "S2 rule3"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(red)
  traffic_light_distance_leq(5)
then
  stop
end

rule "S2 rule4"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(green)
  is_emergence_stop
then
  launch
end
```

4 Scenario 4 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S5 rule1"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(red)
  traffic_light_distance_leq(2)
then
  stop
end

rule "S5 rule2"
trigger always condition is_traffic_light(green)
then
  max_plan_speed(72)
  cruise_speed(40)
end

rule "S5 rule3"
trigger
  always
condition
  is_traffic_light(green)
  is_emergence_stop
then
  launch
end
```

5 Scenario 5 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S7 rule1"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  is_fast_lane  
  speed_smaller(72)  
then  
  max_plan_speed(72)  
  cruise_speed(72)  
  change_lane(right,1)  
end  
  
rule "S7 rule2"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  !is_fast_lane  
  speed_over(40)  
then  
  max_plan_speed(40)  
  cruise_speed(40)  
end
```

6 Scenario 6 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S8 rule1"  
trigger always condition is_raining  
then  
  max_plan_speed(30)  
  cruise_speed(30)  
end  
  
rule "S8 rule2"  
trigger always condition is_foggy  
then  
  max_plan_speed(30)  
  cruise_speed(30)  
end  
  
rule "S8 rule3"  
trigger always condition is_snowing  
then  
  max_plan_speed(30)  
  cruise_speed(30)  
end
```

7 Scenario 7 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S10 rule1"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  is_jam  
  intersection_distance_leq(10)  
then  
  max_plan_speed(0)  
  cruise_speed(0)  
  stop  
end  
  
rule "S10 rule2"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  !is_jam  
  intersection_distance_leq(50)  
then  
  launch  
end
```

8 Scenario 8 driving strategy repairs

```
rule "S11 rule1"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  front_vehicle_closer_than(10.4)  
  speed_over(10)  
then  
  stop  
end  
  
rule "S11 rule2"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  front_vehicle_closer_than(25)  
  speed_smaller(10)  
then  
  launch  
end  
  
rule "S11 rule3"  
trigger  
  always  
condition  
  front_vehicle_closer_than(5)  
  intersection_distance_leq(50)  
then  
  max_plan_speed(40)  
  cruise_speed(11)  
  launch  
end
```